

Research Article

Essential Protocol Update for Inducing Psoriasis in Mice with Imiquimod

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Abstract: Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin condition affecting up to 11% of adults and 1.4% of children globally. It leads to debilitating skin lesions with a psychological impact and a significant reduction in quality of life. The imiquimod (IMQ)-induced psoriatic mouse is a popular model for pathogenesis and intervention studies in discovering new treatments. However, the protocol for this model is unclear, leading to unsatisfactory lesion formation. This is challenging for intervention studies where the lesion would resolve too soon, with insufficient time for significant treatment observation. This article aims to present an improved version of the IMQ-induction protocol for achieving optimal psoriatic morphology. Method: Ten female BALB/c mice, aged 8 to 12 weeks, were divided into original (N=5) and revised protocol (N=5) groups. IMQ was applied on the shaved backs of the mice. In the revised group, the area of IMQ application was set to 4 cm² from the nape of the neck to the posterior thorax. The rest of the steps are the same. The mice in the improved protocol showed higher Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI) scores at the end of six days (original vs. improved group: 4.5 vs. 10, p<0.05). Conclusion: The application of IMQ at a higher back area led to an enhanced psoriasis lesion in a mouse model. By following these refined steps, the reliability and reproducibility of the experiments are enhanced, ultimately allowing for more significant findings in psoriasis research.

Keywords: Psoriasis; imiquimod; mouse model.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder with multisystem involvement, affecting up to 11.4% of adults and 1.4% of children globally (Feldman, 2024). A recent Malaysian Psoriasis Registry data reported 8,813 patients suffering from psoriasis in 34 public and private hospitals nationwide

(Robinson, Tang, Voo et al., 2024). The most common clinical presentation of this condition is raised scaly skin plaques over the extensor aspect of the limbs, face, and scalp (Feldman & Bhutani, 2024), resulting in a significant psychological impact on the patient, considerably reducing their quality of life (Feldman & Bhutani, 2024).

Histologically, the affected skin shows hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, psoriasiform acanthosis, increased intraepidermal and dermal inflammation, and increased capillary density in the rete-ridges (Balan, Grigoraş, Popovici et al., 2019; Kimmel & Lebwohl, 2018). Since there is no cure for this condition, patients need long-term therapy (Feldman & Bhutani, 2024; Robinson et al., 2024), consisting of topical treatment, systemic medication, phototherapy, and biologics (Robinson et al., 2024). Patients frequently require alternative therapies when they encounter treatment failure (Feldman & Bhutani, 2024). Therefore, research for better treatment is ongoing. This requires an understanding of the pathogenesis of the disease since this will allow the identification of potential targets for drug development (Mihu, Neag, Bocşan et al., 2021).

Animal models are frequently utilised in these studies; one of the most popular is mice with imiquimod-induced psoriasis-like skin lesions (Jabeen, Boisgard, Danoy et al., 2020). This mouse psoriasis model has been used in over 100 publications due to its ease of use and low cost (Alsabbagh, 2023). Imiquimod (IMQ) is a ligand for toll-like receptor 7 and 8 (Horváth, Komlódi, Perkecz et al., 2019; Schön, Manzke, & Erpenbeck, 2021). Stimulation of the receptor induces an inflammatory response within the mice (van der Fits, Mourits, Voerman et al., 2009). The induced skin lesions show hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, and acanthosis, with increased capillary density, parallel with the psoriasis lesions in humans.

The original protocol for inducing psoriasis with IMQ application was described by van der Fits et al. (van der Fits et al., 2009). However, the resultant skin lesion may show attenuated psoriasis features as evaluated by Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI) score. This is a clinical scale where the skin redness, thickness, and scaliness are scored using a 5-point Likert scale of 0, none; 1, mild; 2, moderate; 3, severe; 4, very severe. This has resulted in some research groups increasing the duration of IMQ induction (Alsabbagh, 2023).

In the initial part of this study, repeated experiments yielded only mild psoriasis lesions at the end of the induction period. There was a concern that the mice may lick the application area, leading to a reduced effect. However, with a few modifications, we managed to get lesions with higher PASI scores, enabling the proper conduct of the downstream intervention study. This article aims to provide a revised methodology for IMQ-induced psoriasis producing clinically significant psoriasis-like lesions in BALB/c mice.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study was approved by the Animal Research and Ethical Committee, Faculty of Medicine, UiTM, Sungai Buloh (ACUC-1/13). Ten 8–to 12-week-old female BALB/c mice (Chenur supplier, Malaysia) were acclimatised for two weeks before the experiment. The animals were kept in separate cages, maintained at room temperature of 22 ± 2 °C on a 12-hour light/dark cycle and given a pelleted standard diet (Chenur Supplier, Malaysia) and water *ad libitum*. They were divided into two groups of five animals per group: original (OP) and revised (RP) protocol groups.

In the original protocol, the mice's backs were shaved from the mid-thorax to the lower lumbar area (Figure 1 (a)); 62.5mg 5% Imiquimod (IMQ) cream (Aldara; 3M Pharmaceuticals, England) was

applied to the shaved backs for six consecutive days, according to the protocol described by van der Fits et al. (van der Fits et al., 2009). The skin changes were scored using the PASI score on the sixth day.

For the RP group, the nape of the neck to the thorax was shaved, approximately four cm² (Figure 1b). For six consecutive days, 62.5 mg of 5% IMQ was applied to this area, equivalent to 15.6mg of 5% IMQ per cm². At the end of the sixth day, PASI scoring was performed.

3. FINDINGS

The revised group has a more pronounced psoriasis-like lesion than the original group (Figure 1), with a higher overall PASI score (10 vs 4, =0.04; independent sample Mann-Whitney test). In addition, all the PASI parameters score is higher in the RP group.

4. DISCUSSION

This study found that revising the area of the IMQ application to the upper back leads to better lesion formation than in the lower back area. It has been recognised that the mice ingest IMQ upon application on their back by licking the area of application (Grine, Steeland, Van Ryckeghem et al., 2016). The mice have been observed to scratch the area of IMQ application, then lick or bite the hind toes (Sakai, Sanders, Youssef et al., 2016). Thus, oral transfer is still possible due to scratching, foot licking, or biting. Furthermore, IMQ-treated mice gut microbiota composition was found to be significantly different compared to non-treated (Shinno-Hashimoto, Hashimoto, Wei et al., 2021). Interestingly, in the IMQ group, the gut and skin microbiota correlated with each other (Shinno-Hashimoto et al., 2021).

Ingestion of IMQ leads to activation of systemic inflammation, leading to splenomegaly, increased serum inflammatory markers and even death of the animal (Horváth et al., 2019). It has been reported that IMQ skin treatment in animals leads to gastrointestinal production of type I interferon (IFN), which enhances skin inflammation (Grine et al., 2016). This was proven when mice fixed with a collar (Elizabethan collar) to prevent licking expressed significantly reduced psoriasis formation and lower PASI scores (Grine et al., 2016). However, another study, using the Finn chamber to apply Aldara on the mice's skin while preventing scratching and licking of the cream, showed that the skin lesion was comparable to the original protocol, but the systemic effects were reduced (Horváth et al., 2019).

Other than using an Elizabethan collar or a Finn chamber to prevent licking the experiment area, applying the cream higher up the back may also help to avoid this, as the mice could not reach this area to lick it. This may be an explanation of the observed result.

Another point in this study is the area of application of 4 cm², or 15.6mg 5% IMQ per cm². The empirically determined IMQ dosage for induction of psoriasis is 3.125 mg of IMQ per mouse per day, which translates to 62.5 mg of 5% IMQ cream (Aldara) (van der Fits et al., 2009). The original protocol applies this amount to the mouse's shaved back and right ear (van der Fits et al., 2009). A few other studies specified the dosage on the right ear as 5 mg IMQ per day, apart from the skin application of 62.5 mg (Salwa, Badanthadka, & D'Souza, 2021; Sun, Zhang, Xu et al., 2019).

The surface area (cm²) of skin treated with IMQ is frequently not stated in the literature (Horváth et al., 2019; Jabeen et al., 2020; Lin, Yang, Chen et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2019; Swindell, Michaels, Sutter et al., 2017; van der Fits et al., 2009). Among studies that state this parameter, the reported area is 6 cm² (Alvarez & Jensen, 2016) (resulting in a dosage of IMQ of 10.4 mg/cm²), and 20 mg/cm² IMQ

(Sun, Zhao, & Hu, 2013). The original protocol by van der Fitts et al. (van der Fitts et al., 2009) did not specify the dosage per skin area.

The area described by van der Fitts et al. is the backs of the mice and the back of the right ear (van der Fitts et al., 2009). Some researchers apply it on the back of the mice, forgoing the ear (Li, Liu, Gao et al., 2021). The advantage of applying it on the ear is that its thickness is easier to measure than the back skin. The disadvantage is that this area has very thin skin, a far cry from human skin, and thus is of questionable application or comparison to humans. In addition, the mouse's ear is too thin, making it difficult to score with PASI fully. Indeed, the only parameter that is effectively scored is the thickness. In contrast, the skin of the back is thicker, with an epidermis, dermis, and subcutis layer, as in humans' skin.

5. SOLUTION

The revised procedure successfully addresses poor lesion induction in the IMQ psoriasis mouse model. Moving the IMQ treatment area proximally is simple and does not require an extra device or increased cost.

6. IMPACTS

The resultant lesion has a high PASI score and exhibits good histological similarity with human psoriasis. The high PASI score will allow better judgement when scoring the skin response in intervention research.

7. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL,

The revised protocol is an improved version of the original protocol. Its publication can assist researchers in improving the lesion produced and promote more research on the disease. The publication of this protocol is hoped to enhance the institution's good name internationally. The new treatment discovered using this technique will bring about commercial potential.

Figure 1. (a) The back of the mice showing an area clear of hair, removed using Veet cream. (b and c) Comparison between the results from two different IMQ application areas in BALB/c mice. In (b), the lesion has a much higher PASI score than (c), with a higher level of redness, skin thickening and scaling. For both, 62.5 mg IMQ (Aldara) was applied to the shaved area; in (b), the area is approximately 4x1 cm, while in (c), it is approximately 5x2 cm. The higher concentration of IMQ led to a more pronounced lesion. (d) Photomicrograph of a good psoriatic lesion showing hyperplasia of the epidermis (black arrow) with hyperkeratosis (blue arrow).

8. CONCLUSION

This revised protocol allows for successful morphological induction of psoriasis with imiquimod. The IMQ is applied from the lower neck to the thorax area of the back, with a dosage of approximately 15 mg/cm².

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References

- Alsabbagh, M. (2023). Imiquimod-induced psoriasis model: induction protocols, model characterization and factors adversely affecting the model. *Acta biochimica Polonica*. https://doi.org/10.18388/abp.2020_6426
- Alvarez, P., & Jensen, L. E. (2016). Imiquimod Treatment Causes Systemic Disease in Mice Resembling Generalized Pustular Psoriasis in an IL-1 and IL-36 Dependent Manner. *Mediators of Inflammation*, 2016(1), 6756138. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/6756138>
- Balan, R., Grigoraş, A., Popovici, D., & Amălinei, C. (2019). The histopathological landscape of the major psoriasiform dermatoses. *Arch Clin Cases*, 6(3), 59-68. <https://doi.org/10.22551/2019.24.0603.10155>
- Feldman, S. R. (2024). Psoriasis: Epidemiology, Clinical Manifestations and Diagnosis. UpToDate. Retrieved 26/9/2024, from https://www-uptodate-com.uitm.idm.oclc.org/contents/psoriasis-epidemiology-clinical-manifestations-and-diagnosis?search=psoriasis&source=search_result&selectedTitle=1%7E150&usage_type=default&display_rank=1
- Feldman, S. R., & Bhutani, T. (2024). Chronic plaque psoriasis in adults: Overview of management. In R. P. Dellavalle & K. C. Duffin (Eds.), UpToDate. Wolters Kluwer.
- Grine, L., Steeland, S., Van Ryckeghem, S., Ballegeer, M., Lienenklaus, S., Weiss, S., Sanders, N. N., Vandenbroucke, R. E., & Libert, C. (2016). Topical imiquimod yields systemic effects due to unintended oral uptake. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 20134. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep20134>
- Horváth, S., Komlódi, R., Perkecz, A., Pintér, E., Gyulai, R., & Kemény, Á. (2019). Methodological refinement of Aldara-induced psoriasiform dermatitis model in mice. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 3685. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-39903-x>
- Jabeen, M., Boisgard, A. S., Danoy, A., El Kholti, N., Salvi, J. P., Bouliou, R., Fromy, B., Verrier, B., & Lamrayah, M. (2020). Advanced Characterization of Imiquimod-Induced Psoriasis-Like Mouse Model. *Pharmaceutics*, 12(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12090789>
- Kimmel, G. W., & Lebwohl, M. (2018). Psoriasis: Overview and Diagnosis. *Evidence-Based Psoriasis*, 1–16. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-90107-7_1
- Li, Q., Liu, W., Gao, S., Mao, Y., & Xin, Y. (2021). Application of imiquimod-induced murine psoriasis model in evaluating interleukin-17A antagonist. *BMC Immunology*, 22(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12865-021-00401-3>
- Lin, Y. K., Yang, S. H., Chen, C. C., Kao, H. C., & Fang, J. Y. (2015). Using Imiquimod-Induced Psoriasis-Like Skin as a Model to Measure the Skin Penetration of Anti-Psoriatic Drugs. *PLoS One*, 10(9), e0137890. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0137890>
- Mihu, C., Neag, M. A., Bocşan, I. C., Melincovici, C. S., Vesa Ş, C., Ionescu, C., Baican, A. L., Lisencu, L. A., & Buzoianu, A. D. (2021). Novel concepts in psoriasis: histopathology and markers related to modern treatment approaches. *Rom J Morphol Embryol*, 62(4), 897-906. <https://doi.org/10.47162/rjme.62.4.02>
- Robinson, S., Tang, M. M., Voo, S. Y. M., Ramalingam, R., Selvarajah, L., Jamil, A., Kwan, Z., & Loo, C. H. (2024). The twelfth report of the Malaysian Psoriasis Registry 2020-2022, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia 2024 (A. Johar, C. C.C., & W. C. Tan, Eds.). *The Malaysian Psoriasis Registry*.

- Sakai, K., Sanders, K. M., Youssef, M. R., Yanushefski, K. M., Jensen, L., Yosipovitch, G., & Akiyama, T. (2016). Mouse model of imiquimod-induced psoriatic itch. *Pain*, 157(11), 2536-2543. <https://doi.org/10.1097/j.pain.0000000000000674>
- Salwa, F., Badanthadka, M., & D'Souza, L. (2021). Differential Psoriatic Effect of Imiquimod on Balb/c and Swiss Mice. *Journal of Health and Allied Sciences NU*, 11(03), 170-177. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1726681>
- Schön, M. P., Manzke, V., & Erpenbeck, L. (2021). Animal models of psoriasis – highlights and drawbacks. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 147(2), 439-455. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2020.04.034>
- Shinno-Hashimoto, H., Hashimoto, Y., Wei, Y., Chang, L., Fujita, Y., Ishima, T., Matsue, H., & Hashimoto, K. (2021). Abnormal composition of microbiota in the gut and skin of imiquimod-treated mice. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 11265. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-90480-4>
- Sun, J., Zhao, Y., & Hu, J. (2013). Curcumin inhibits imiquimod-induced psoriasis-like inflammation by inhibiting IL-1beta and IL-6 production in mice. *PLoS One*, 8(6), e67078. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0067078>
- Sun, S., Zhang, X., Xu, M., Zhang, F., Tian, F., Cui, J., Xia, Y., Liang, C., Zhou, S., Wei, H., Zhao, H., Wu, G., Xu, B., Liu, X., Yang, G., Wang, Q., Zhang, L., Gong, Y., Shao, C., & Zou, Y. (2019). Berberine downregulates CDC6 and inhibits proliferation via targeting JAK-STAT3 signaling in keratinocytes. *Cell Death Dis*, 10(4), 274. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41419-019-1510-8>
- Swindell, W. R., Michaels, K. A., Sutter, A. J., Diaconu, D., Fritz, Y., Xing, X., Sarkar, M. K., Liang, Y., Tsoi, A., Gudjonsson, J. E., & Ward, N. L. (2017). Imiquimod has strain-dependent effects in mice and does not uniquely model human psoriasis. *Genome Med*, 9(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-017-0415-3>
- van der Fits, L., Mourits, S., Voerman, J. S., Kant, M., Boon, L., Laman, J. D., Cornelissen, F., Mus, A. M., Floencia, E., Prens, E. P., & Lubberts, E. (2009). Imiquimod-induced psoriasis-like skin inflammation in mice is mediated via the IL-23/IL-17 axis. *J Immunol*, 182(9), 5836-5845. <https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.0802999>